

Microplastic Particles in Food

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The term *microplastic* is used for small plastic particles of different origins, sizes and chemical composition. The exact sizes of microplastics have not been uniformly defined in the relevant literature, they mostly range from 0.001 mm to less than 5 mm. Basically, two types of microplastics are distinguished, primary and secondary microplastic. Primary microplastic is specifically produced industrially in the form of plastic-based granulates or pellets. Secondary microplastic occurs through chemical and physical ageing and degradation processes in products such as plastic bags and plastic bottles. As far as can be ascertained today, secondary microplastic is the main source of entry into the environment.

Currently, the Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) does not have any reliable data on the chemical composition, particle size or concentration of microplastic particles in food. Due to a lack of robust data, a health risk assessment of the consumption of food contaminated with microplastic particles is presently not possible. The BfR has requested the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) for a scientific opinion on the occurrence of microplastic and nanoplastic particles in food, especially in seafood.

The full version of this BfR Opinion is available in German on <http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/mikroplastikpartikel-in-lebensmitteln.pdf>